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Afri-Culture Influence Of Gender-Leadership Inequality On Theological Institutions: A Case Study Of The Nigerian Baptist Convention

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ABSTRACT

It is observed that Christian theological institutions in Nigeria are patriarchal in nature when it comes to the office of the president, rector or provost. This is attributed to the influence of Afri-culture of leadership gender inequality on the system. This observation gave rise to the title "the Afri-Culture Influence of Leadership Gender Inequality on Theological Institutions: A Case Study of the Nigerian Baptist Convention. The writer used descriptive research method, and interaction with related materials to discuss Afri-culture influence of leadership gender inequality in the Nigerian Baptist Convention, noting that competent women could be encourage and given chance to also serve as president, rector or provost of the institutions. This could erase marginalization of women in the system. To actualize this goal, women should be encourage to compete with men; religious body should approach the concept of leader and leadership from the secular arena; structure should be put in place to allow only qualified women to compete when there is vacancy in a given period; search committee should add theocratic system of choosing a candidate to their requirements of choice, and all should know that a call to the ministry is a call to serve, therefore women are equally qualified to manage the theological institutions. If the above recommendations are put into practice then, the wealth of knowledge of competent women would be beneficial to all and sundries.

Keywords: Afri-culture, Gender, Leadership Inequality; Theological Education.

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian Baptist Convention is one of the indigenous Christian denominations to be reckoned with in Nigeria. She has well-structured organogram with the sole aim of reaching the unreached for Christ. This is a mission minded Christian denomination. The mission mindedness spur her to raise called trained leaders through the various theological institutions established to have qualified personnel of international repute alongside with moral and spiritual standard. However, it has been observed that since the inception of her theological institutions that award various educational degrees such as Certificate in Theology (CTh), Diploma in Theology/Religious Education (DTh/DRE), Bachelor in Theology/Religious Education (BTh/BRE); Bachelor in Mission; Master of Divinity in Missiology (M. Div. Miss); Bachelor in Church Music (BCM) Master in Church Music (MCM); Master in Theology/Religious Education (MTh/MRE) Master in Philosophy (M. Phil); Doctor in Ministry (D. Min); and Doctor in Philosophy (PhD); None of the theological institutions has been led by women in spite of their qualifications, except in recent times that only two women were given opportunities to head the Baptist Theological Seminary, Eku, Delta State; and Baptist College of Theology, Oyo, Oyo State Nigeria.

This article discusses the patriarchal approach to leadership in theological institutions using Nigerian Baptist Convention as a case study in order to have a taste of a leader who is a woman either as a Rector, Provost, and President to avoid the syndrome of marginalization. In view of the above, the

article is divided into sections, namely: a brief history of some Baptist Theological Institutions of the Nigeria Baptist Convention, African culture of gender inequality of leadership; leadership in Nigeria Baptist Theological institutions; and the way forward.

A Brief History of Some Baptist Theological Institutions of the Nigerian Baptist Convention

In this section, to highlight gender inequality in the leadership of theological institutions in the Nigerian Baptist Convention, I discuss the brief history of select theological institutions of the Nigerian Baptist Convention. The select institutions are the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso; Baptist Theological Seminary, Eku, Nigeria; and Baptist Theological Seminary, Kaduna, Nigeria.

Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso, Oyo State.

Oroniran (2013), quoted Cecil Roberson who published an article titled "Baptist theological Seminary: How it all Began" said that the Old Baptist Training School grew out of the preacher training plan by Rev. Charles Edwin Smith for members of the old Oshupa congregation, Ogbomoso from 1891 to 1897 and it began officially on May 3, 1898 in the Old Oke Oshupa Baptist Chapel and by 1920 to 1936, theological training was administered as part of the Baptist College and Seminary in Ogbomoso and by 1934, Dr. F. C Pool joined the staff of the institution with special responsibilities for Theological training. Oronian noted that in 1948, the seminary was officially affiliated to the Southern Baptist! Theological Seminary, Louisville, Kentucky, USA. By this arrangement, qualified students trained at the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso, have been granted degrees by the Southern Baptist Theological Seminary, Louisville, Kentucky; thus the first Bachelor of Theology degrees were awarded were in 1950, the grandaunts having satisfied the requirements for graduation in 1948, making the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary (NBTS), Oghomoso to become the first tertiary institution to award degrees in Nigeria. The Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso began its Bachelor of Religious Education (BRE) programme in 1970, conferring its first degree in 1973. Today, the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso awards Diploma (Phased out in June, 2003, except in Church Music), graduate and post-graduate degrees in Theology, Religious Education, Church Music; and Missiology.

The Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso became a post-graduate school with effect from 2002. Similarly, all the Baptist Colleges of Theology in Southern Nigeria, such as Benin ~City, Eku (now upgraded to Seminary status), Igede -Ekiti, Lagos, Obinze-Owerri, and Oyo, all operating under the proprietorship of the Nigerian Baptist Convention, affiliated to the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso, with effect from the 2002/2003 academic session for proper co-ordination and quality control of the programmes.

Baptist Theological Seminary, Eku, Nigeria

According to the Baptist Theological Seminary, Eku, Catalogue (2020-2025), the Baptist Theological Seminary, Eku, Delta State, Nigeria was established in 1945 by American Missionaries named Rev. Dr. and Mrs. W. H. Carson who died on May 20, 1954. The institution started as Baptist Bible School. At the initial stage the institution appeared to be mobile because it operated from the location(s) of the foreign missionary; thus, the movement of the missionaries ensured the movement of the school. From 1956 to 1958 Rev. O. C. Robinson became the principal of the School in Benin City before relocating the school to Warri.

Meanwhile the Nigerian Civil War (1967-1970) forced Rev. and Mrs. Z. D Reece to relocate from Nsukka to Eku in 1967. Rev. Reece assumed the principal-ship of the Bible School, and restructured its academic and administrative systems. Consequently, the three years academic system for the Certificate in Theology began on January 9, 1968. The institution evolved from Bible School to Baptist College of Theology, and has now been upgraded to a Seminary. In line with the *Catalogue*, the following principals and presidents have served in administrative capacities, which include: Rev W. H. Carson (1945-1954), Rev. O.C Robison (1956 -1959); Dr. T. B Gaultney (1959-1960); Rev. G. E. Robison (1961-1965); Rev. Urban Green (1966-1966) Rev. Hurst (1961-1965), Rev. B. Donaldson (1967); Rev. Z. D. Reece (1968-1972); Rev. Gene Legg (1972).

The indigenous administrators of the institutions are Rev. P. E. Ofuoku (1972-1996); Rev. A. I. Ifukor (1996-1999); Rev. Dr. G. O. Anie (1999-2007); Rev. Dr. M. O Oladeji (2007-2008); Rev. Dr. GF. N. Aghawenu (2008-2019) and Rev. Prof. (Mrs.) Helen Ishola-Esan, the current President of the Seminary whose tenure started in July 2019. The Baptist Theological Seminary, Eku, Nigeria offers

Certificate in Theology, Diploma in Religions Education, Diploma in Theology; and Diploma in Chinch Music. The Seminary also offers Bachelor of Church Music, Bachelor of Theology, and Bachelor in Religious Education. Furthermore, the Seminary offers Master of Divinity in Religious Education; Master of Divinity in Theology; and Master of Divinity in Church Music programmes.

Brief History of Baptist Theological Seminary, Kaduna

Baptist Theological Seminary, Kaduna, as stated in her catalogue (2020-2025) began quite modestly in 1948. It was when Dr. Charles Knight and his wife, the first Baptist missionary to reside North of River Niger, started training some Hausa speaking Christians who felt called to preach for a few weeks each year. In 1950 when Dr. and Mrs. Knight returned to America, Dr. Farrell E. Reneyan and his wife came up to work in Kaduna. They continued to meet with these Hausa-speaking Christians for a few weeks a year until the arrival of Mrs. Bonnie Moore in 1952. Additional hands were made available, therefore it was decided that regular classes should be held each year for a six-months period. It was also agreed that a certificate would be awarded upon completion, of three six-month period. In January 1953, the Hausa Baptist Pastor School began a formal course of study. And in 1956, the school moved to its present location in Hayin Bank, Kawo, Kaduna. The name of the School was changed in 1994 from the Baptist Pastors School to Baptist Theological Seminary Kaduna due to its upgraded status. The following served as leaders of the School: Rev. Parah Hal and Mr. T. A. Oke. In June 1999 Rev. Dr. Charles Hedricks handed over to Rev. Dr. B. Uche Enyioha, then Rev. Dr. Reuben I. Chuga became the president in 1 June 2009. And in 2019, Dr. R. I. Chuga handed over to Rev Prof. Moses Audi who is still there till now.

African Culture of Gender Inequality of Leadership

The issue of culture is very important because it affects the totality of man. It is the mirror of identifying people's group which involves their ways of doing things. In Africa, some people look at culture as the preserved traditions of the forefathers. However, according to Ajayi (2005), culture connotes the aggregate of total human inventions and discovery; and the summation of all socially acquired human characteristics. In order words, culture consists of patterns of behavior that define a people's perception of right and wrong, good and bad, beauty and ugliness, truth and falsehood, life and even death. From another perspective, Marvin (1983) look at culture as the learnt socially acquired tradition and life-styles of a society, including its patterned and repetitive ways of thinking, feeling, and acting. It is an ongoing social heritage and it defines a people way of life.

In Africa, culture of gender inequality is a social heritage that defines status of male and females' position in the home and in the society. For example, the Urhobo people of Delta State, Nigeria esteem the position of a male child than that of a female child irrespective of their age differences. That is one of the reasons why a first son undermines his female siblings that were born before him; he will take the lion share of their father's estate when he is no longer alive. According to Odje (2011), the eldest son inherits his deceased father's dwelling house. This is done before other distribution of the estate is made. The above act is not limited to Urhobo People of Delta State, Nigeria alone; it cuts across African ethnic groups. That is the reason why most women are marginalized in African context. This is in line with Jegede (2015) that in Africa Women are not allowed to occupy highest leadership positions in traditional setting.

In the same vein, Gbenda (2006) posited that women's struggle for equality and equity has taken them to a job formally believed to be the exclusive reserves for men because men are believed to be better suited for jobs involving hard work, emotional stress and responsibilities of leadership, such as forces/para-military service. That assertion is part of African culture of gender inequality for there could be no tedious and emotional stressful service like the office of national president. It is on record, Equavoen (2017) that Ellen Johnson Sir leaf was elected as Liberian President and Sworn in on January 16th 2006, and Miss Felix Stella at the age of 17years travelled to the space on September, 2006. These are some examples of females who broke that jinx of gender inequality. Those women are Africans but were given equal opportunity with men and were able to contribute their wealth of knowledge to develop their nations.

In African culture, the image of women is very low. They are seen as inferior to men. In most cases culturally, they are seen as just men's properties (Danfulani, 2002). In addition to that, women in African culture are men's subordinate. Some men even see women as tools through which children are born to keep the society growing, surely, that concept is true, then by implication women appear to

even contribute more in terms of keeping the society alive than men; and in that case, it is injustice to them for not allowing them to be among those on the platform of leadership in theological institutions. There is a saying that goes, whom the cap fits, let him/her wear it. Gender inclusivity in leadership ought to cut across all spheres of humanity, including theological institutions, since women are also human beings born to contribute their talent towards enhancing the development of the same society.

Influence of Afri-culture of Gender Inequality on Leadership in Baptist Theological Institutions

In discussing the influence of Afri-culture of gender inequality on leadership of theological institutions in the Nigerian Baptist Convention, there is need to clarify some key terms. These include gender, inequality and leadership. Gender, to Oladeinde (2014), refers to the different socially prescribed roles of males and females in a society; and FAO (1997) is of the view that gender is a central organizing principle of societies that often governs the processes of production and reproduction. From the above positions, gender depicts functional prescriptive for males and females, which affects social bio-economic of a given society. It is like caste method in hinduism whereby the brahmins seat atop as the privileged class, followed by Kahtriyas (the warriors,) the vaisyas (the artisan, the farmers and the merchants) and finally the sudras who are the servants or labourers according to Omoregbe (2018). In that case, there are limitations and boundaries in life, which will also affect the impute or contributions of an individual even though he or she is intelligent with good vision for the growth and development of the society. Again, the cultural inequality is not only practice by African traditional people but also in Islam as seen in News and Eric (2002), in Islam, the law of inheritance further determines that a male offspring gets double the inheritance of a female and in Islamic courts of justice man's witness is worth twice that of a woman. From that assertion, women in Islam are inferior to men just as in African culture. In some African people's groups, a girl child does not inherit her father's or parent properties, she is seen as another man's wife outside her own family and she has such right in her husband compound only, such culture or practice places more value on a male child. In some ethnic group in Africa, some individual men had divorced their wives for giving birth to only female children on the notion that they have not born because they have only given birth to female children. Thus, in some African cultural homes, a girl child is not educated because she is born to marry and have her own children. However, due to orientation, an awareness has be created for female children to be educated, just like their male counterpart.

Inequality in this context simply means the domination of one above the other to Nehls and Erick (2002) in Islam like Africa culture, it is a male domination over female in spite of their qualifications and capabilities which may hinder all-inclusiveness in terms of leadership. The term, leadership, according to Haggai (2013), is a discipline of exerting special influence within a group towards the attainment of goals that meet the group's real needs. To Adeloje (2011) who quoted Peter G. Wiwcharuckis' definition of leadership, leadership is an art of combining ideas, people, things, time, Leadership and faith to achieve set objectives. In the same direction Onokonvwen (2010) posited that leadership is the ability to direct others. From the foregoing, I concur that leadership is the act of motivating a group to actualize set goals. In addition to that, the application of leadership is not limited to sex but for those whom the cap fits. In the words of Adetunji (2010) as he related it to the church, leadership in the local church is the noble art of cooperatively planning and achieving the goals God has set for humankind in the life, teaching, death, resurrection and the coming back of Jesus, the Christ. However, it appears that those concepts are more of theories than practice as observed by the researcher in the Nigerian Baptist Theological Institutions. Some interested qualified women can only be allowed to lecture in the institutions and such it appears that there are unseen bars across their aspirations created by culture.

The Nigerian Baptist Convention has ten (10) theological institutions, which include: the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso; Baptist college of Theology, Igede Ekiti; Baptist Theological Seminary, Kaduna; Baptist College of Theology, Lagos; Baptist College of Theology, Oyo; Baptist College of Theology, Benin City; Baptist College of Theology, Obinze, Owerri; Baptist Pastors School, Gombi; and Baptist Theological Seminary, Eku. Since the inception of those institutions none, except two in recent times, has been led by women. From the book of reports of the Nigerian Baptist Convention (2016) all the theological leaders who reported at the 103rd Annual Convention-in-session held in Ilorin, Kwara State were men, and one of the institutions is as old as the convention, this was born in 1914. It may interest one to know without prejudice the brain behind the

scene is the influence of Afri-culture of gender, on inequality since many women of the same faith are spiritually and academically qualified.

The Afri-culture of gender inequality is similar to the culture practice of the Middle East where Judaism, Christianity and Islam originated from. In line with Awolalu (1976), the Eastern society is patriarchal in nature, authority rests on the father, who is the head of the family; and since the three religions emanated from that kind of environment, unavoidably, they have imbibed the prevailing culture. That is the situation some Nigerian Baptist qualified women find themselves and the struggle continue.

This is not so with secular institutions either private or public. For example, the Western-Delta University, Oghara, Delta State, has a female Vice Chancellor (VC). Also, the Rector of Delta State Polytechnic, Otefe, Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria is a woman. Beside those, qualified women are head mistress and principals at primary and secondary school levels. Those are some instances where women serve as leaders in secular higher education in Nigeria. Those women have the same components with their counter part in the Baptist faith. It appears that the understanding of leadership in the secular world is different from that of the ecclesiastical. The Secular addresses issues as related to the concept of leadership, while in the religious order, the influence of African culture defines who is to be a leader in certain positions. This seems to be the plight of women in the apex position of leadership in Baptist theological institutions, which need to be addressed in order for qualified women to exercise their gifts and hard work in education and utilize them for the benefit of the religious body in particular and the nation in general. In academics, some of the women are professors, and senior lecturers lecturing in the same theological institutions with their men counterpart. This raises another issue, that if they can lecture in the same institution, why can they not be allowed to head the institution as they contribute to human development and capacity building which eventually raises those institutions to a higher standard?

The Way Forward

It appears that some qualified Baptist women are just enduring the situation of not being allowed to participate in the struggle of selecting a leader to manage theology institutions. On that ground, they should be encouraged to compete with qualified interested men when necessary. Again, religious body should approach the concept of leader and leadership from the secular arena which is devoid of cultural gender inequality; thus, the possibility of Afri-culture of general inequity to influence the system will be minimized. More still, a structure should be put in place by a religious body to allow qualified women to compete when there is vacancy at a given period. This is to avoid men domination in the arena. Furthermore, a search of any theological institution to choose President, Rector or Provost should grow beyond academic qualification and level of spirituality to include a theocracy that allows God to select for them. When it is done appropriately, the will of God will come to pass. Thus, it will minimize human politics. Lastly, the religious body should know that officers in any theological institutions are called to serve. Since the understanding of call to the ministry today is all inclusive, then competent women could equally be called to manage them including the apex office.

CONCLUSION

This article discussed the Afri-culture influence of gender-leadership inequality in Nigerian Baptist Convention owned theological institutions. The study highlighted the history of select theological institutions of the Nigerian Baptist Convention, noting the dominance of male in their leadership from 198 till date, stating the impact of Mid-Eastern culture on biblical narratives which mix African patriarchal culture to enable gender inequality in the apex leaderships of the theological institutions. Furthermore, the research linked the status of women in theological institutions leadership of the Nigerian Baptist Convention to the status of women in Islamic religion and jurisprudence, unlike the status of women in secular tertiary education institutions in Delta State, Nigeria, where women lead; and called for gender inclusivity and equality in the apex leadership positions of the theological institutions through cultural re-orientation, emphasis on personal competences and spirituality, and the will of God. The implementation of these recommendations is capable of contributing towards the eradication of Afri-culture influence of gender-leadership inequality in the Nigerian Baptist Convention owned theological institutions.

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